

Mammal surveying protocol in Rugezi Marshland (north-eastern Rwanda) with application to other tropical wetlands

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Abstract

This field survey protocol was compiled to facilitate researchers who want to conduct surveys in tropical wetlands to find field tools, techniques, and datasheets for future studies in Rugezi Marsh and other tropical wetlands with similar or related characteristics. Fieldwork was conducted in two seasons in 2023: a dry season (June-July) and a wet season (November-December). The results of this survey have excluded bats, but future endeavors will aim to include them to encompass all the mammals found in the high-altitude marshland. All these procedures can be freely adapted by any user and applied without restrictions; however, scholarly papers reporting methods based on this development must cite this reference, noting whether they were adapted.

1. Generalities

Research permit

Check in advance whether any specimens need to be prepared, and ensure compliance with research permit requirements.

Basic equipment

Besides camping facilities and trapping materials, basic field equipment includes:

- Binoculars for observations
- Field notebook or datasheets for recording observations
- Guidebook for identification of species
- Appropriate clothing gear according to the location
- Marking tape
- Measuring tape
- GPS unit or pre-loaded mapping app
- Gloves for handling field stuff
- Digital camera

Additional equipment may depend on the circumstances:

- Compass for specifying directions
- Topographic map or aerial photograph
- Permanent marking pen

Sampling strategy

Categorization of habitats and selection of sampling sites

- Sampling sites should consider the sections of the marshland to ensure spatial coverage. For Rugezi, the northern, central, and southern parts will be selected.
- Sampling sites will consider the types and characteristics of habitats in terms of plant diversity and habitat structure.
- Selection of habitats may also consider types and proximity of surrounding uses, as well as the level of threats or habitat use.
- Ideally, at least two sampling sites with similar characteristics should be compared over the sampling area.

Methods

Selecting the methods to be used.

- A list of methods that should be used for a comprehensive survey of terrestrial mammals on Rugezi Marsh includes camera traps, Sherman traps, pitfall traps, cage traps, sign surveys and observations, and night surveys. Details of each method have been provided.
- If voucher specimens or DNA samples are needed, about two individuals of presumed different species can be taken from the study area, and should not be taken from one site.
- For DNA tissues on live animals that should be released, one alternative to keeping the animal with minimal or almost no harm is to cut the last portion of the tail, which will also be used to recognize recaptures.

Sampling effort

- The researcher will first determine the number of traps to be used according to the number of days, the daily plans, and the area to be covered.
- This will depend on the resources available and the time allocated to the project.
- While the optimal number of traps will be specified later, each sub-site should be surveyed for at least three days of trap visits; two or more sub-sites can be used simultaneously as applicable.

Safety and ethical consideration

- Besides gloves of quality and texture accommodating the characteristics of the animal to be handled, a first-aid kit for possible wounds or bites should always be available before coming close to animals.
- Live trapping is always recommended; should the collection of specimens of whole individuals or any part of the animal be necessary, all permit requirements need to be fulfilled and fairly defined to the competent permit-granting authority; handling should always be humane.
- Unexperienced field assistants should be endowed with sufficient skills in handling animals as necessary prior to field work.

2. Camera traps

Main requirements and considerations

- Consider conducting a reconnaissance visit to the places to check about the likely presence of mammals; however, when sufficient cameras are available, putting some cameras at places where no signs are obvious increases the chance of detecting rare animals.
- Cameras should be deployed based on signs and likelihood, including where signs such as footprints, scats, or feeding signs were observed, and places likely to fulfill the foraging niche for the targeted animals.

Characteristics of camera traps

- The camera traps to be used for the wetlands, like Rugezi, should be of standard quality or above, with colored photos, able to record good-quality videos in addition to the photos.
- If the researcher isn't sufficiently trained, a staff member or expert in charge of preparing traps and fixing proper trap settings should be available.

Trapping design

- A minimum of two camera traps should be placed at one site location, and the camera traps should last an entire field session.
- Regardless of constraints, at least three weeks should be used to ensure sufficient information can be documented by the camera traps, beyond random events.
- Since it is possible to monitor the records by the camera traps, one may consider changing the position of the camera trap to a nearby location at the same site when 3 to 5 days are spent without any record of the targeted species, or when it seems that only the same animal is appearing over and over in the same camera.

Trapping preparation

- Traps will be placed in an open space towards the targeted spot.
- The place will be cleared when there are obstacles that hinder the target from the camera's view.

Placement of traps

- It is often necessary to fix a log or any piece of support on which a camera can be attached, since most wetlands in Rwanda do not have trees but grasses and papyrus; even when a tree is present, it may not provide a proper position for the camera.
- Place the camera towards the position where animals are likely to occur, considering the signs found or the suitability of the habitat.

3. Sherman traps

Main requirements and considerations

- Conduct a pre-field visit for trapping or the general coverage and structure of the site; this will help to reflect in advance on different options for placing the traps.
- Ensure that the different needed baits are present and can be secured in sufficient quantity, or markets are available for sourcing them in case they become short.
- Ensure that a well-trained staff is available for fixing traps, settling traps, handling live rodents, shrews, and allies safely, and preparing baits with proper consistency.
- Dispose of a sufficient number of traps; a possible minimum should be between 15 and 20 traps at one site, while 40 to 50 traps at one site should be ideal.
- Tagging the traps with flagging tapes with an inscription or a sign of the trap number is essential, as such materials can be easily lost or accidentally misplaced.

Characteristics of Sherman traps

- Sherman traps should be of standard sizes and quality, with two main sizes varying from medium (fit for small rodents and shrews of any size) to large (fit for large rodents like the cane rats, or even big pouched rats)

Trapping design

- Sherman traps are promising even when placed indiscriminately at any place around the site, provided that different small sections of the general habitat are covered.
- Once a few successive traps are not promising after at least four days of trapping, small shifts at the same location will be required.
- Traps should be set at one site for at least 5 days; when time allows, traps can be shifted to another location at the same site, rather than staying at one place longer, unless new species are still recorded after the fifth day.
- Traps should be visited each day in the morning, and target nearly the same hours of the day for visiting traps, to avoid that animals caught earlier in traps get more stressed. When time and distance to the lodging place allow, traps would ideally be visited twice a day.
- Whether one chooses line transects, strip transects, reconnaissance trails, or random trails, the chance of capture might be the same, only requiring justification of the choice.

Bait preparation and baiting

- The standard bait for use in Sherman traps is a mixture of peanut butter and white oats; the researcher needs to keep proper proportions to keep the consistency of the resulting bait.
- Bait should be carefully placed in the trap at the rear end to avoid shedding any bait outside the trap or at the wrong place, eventually causing the trap to malfunction.

- Always check if the bait is still there, as one of the predators is ants. Check also its status. Bait should be changed as often as possible during the rainy season.

Placement of traps

- The distance between traps should usually be between 5 and 20 m; this depends on the size of the study area and other characteristics. Especially, Sherman traps need to be concealed from anyone unaware of the activity, as some passers-by may check them, steal them, or inadvertently undo them.
- Along a trail, it is always most efficient to place traps alternately at left and right of the trail, but modifications are due to the characteristics of the sampling area.
- The traps should be settled horizontally so that the animals easily go inside, attracted by the bait, to avoid failures associated with the traps settled with a slope.
- Support on the lateral side or behind could be an asset when a trap may fall or flip easily due to any small disturbance around.

Safety of the animal and the handler

- Cotton balls should be placed in the trap to avoid any death or much stress due to coldness of the trap, wetness due to rainfall, or wetting stress due to poops or urination; they should be changed every time they look no safer after each capture
- Wearing gloves as tough as the ones used in hardware houses is essential in handling small mammals to avoid bites or possible escapes.
- Mesh bags are ideal for collecting the small mammal captured alive from the trap; however, when not available, another type of bag can be used, but requires more vigilance.

4. Pitfall traps

Main requirements and considerations

- While they are live traps and targeting small mammals as Sherman traps do, pitfall traps do not fit at any site; therefore, check beforehand where they are suitable to be placed.

- Three conditions are: sufficient space for placing one uncut pitfall (at least 15-20 meters long), a possible or suitable place for digging spaces for placing buckets, and a suitable place that can accommodate a pitfall without dramatically degrading the existing habitat.
- Experienced staff in making pitfall traps, especially considering the consistency of the wetland site selected, is essential; otherwise, closely supervise a local helper.

Pitfall trap conditions and design

- Pitfall traps are built on plastic sheets (tough consistency is better) and buckets buried under them straddling the plastic sheet on both sides, to ensure that nocturnal or crepuscular rodents or shrews will travel along and encounter it as a barrier and fall into the bucket.
- Baiting isn't necessary at all; only one can try randomly to shed some small bait pieces when captures are scarce.
- Distance between buckets may vary according to the number of available buckets, but two to four meters between buckets is logical.
- Height of bucket may vary, but 30-40 mm should be around the average.
- Small trees or twigs, straight as possible, should be available to ensure the pitfall is upright and well fixed, with strong ropes to attach them to the reusable plastic sheets.

Placement and fixing of pitfalls in wet soils

- Unlike other dry or semi-dry soils, the pits in wetland soils will quickly collect water, and the bucket will eventually be pushed up by the upward pressure of rising water, which will cause the pitfall to disintegrate or the bucket to fill with water.
- A sustainable solution is to fix one or two trees that are inserted on both sides above the bucket to ensure that no water pressure can be able to lift the bucket away.

5. Cage traps

Main requirements and considerations

- Due to the costs of cage traps, an optimal number should only be acquired, i.e., at least three traps at one subsite, to last for a minimum of 3 to 4 days
- Bait for carnivores consists of meat (raw or roasted meat or fish), or sardines from cans, or a mixture of two kinds of baits

- A skilled person to check the trap set-up and its position should be available; all traps should be concealed as much as possible, sometimes adding covering materials
- Consider cage sizes when targeting mammals of different sizes; for example, when one is expecting a serval, a large cage should be placed, rather than the one for a genet.

Characteristics of cage traps

Standard cage traps are made of wire mesh; they can be folding (Tomahawk types) or unfolding (Havahart types).

Trapping design

- Concealing the trap from view and direct sightings by the targeted animals is more essential than the exact locations where signs are found. The researcher will prioritize spaces where traps can be hidden or covered, and an optimal distance according to the site conditions
- According to the observed signs and number of traps, two traps can be settled close or opposite to each other to target both sides where animals might be moving from.

Placement of traps

- Traps should be positioned in a way that the entrance for the trap is free, and other parts of the trap are concealed or not easily accessible by the targeted animals. When possible, push the trap under tall bushes and let the opening face out; you can cover the trap with surrounding vegetation or bend bushes, grasses, or branches over it.
- The cage trap will be settled horizontally or with only slight bending to minimize capture failures when the animal has reached the trap.
- Support the trap from the lateral side or behind when it may fall or flip due to a small disturbance event around

Baiting and bait placement

- The main bait will be placed behind in the rear part of the trap, where the animal advancing to take it will be lured to cause the trigger to release, leading to the closure of the trap; this bait will be fixed with a small rope, strong thread, or tagging tape so that the animal will stay longer struggling to remove it.
- One luring bait will be placed inside near the entrance of the trap, centrally on the bottom of the trap, free, to lure the animal to enter.
- One smaller bait will be placed a few centimeters outside near the entrance for a continued lure to the animal to follow the track.

6. Sign surveys and observations, including the night survey

Methods and procedures

- Prior knowledge of possible species of mammals that might be there is essential to learn about their signs in advance, such as the shape of footprints and the structure of their scats.
- Linear transects, strip transects, reconnaissance trails, or any combination, may be considered, depending on the likelihood of occurrences and diversity of signs.
- It is important to prioritize spaces where trails of animals are more likely for a more active search for signs: signs are often detected according to the known habitat preferences of animals; for ex., one should not target otter signs on dry sites of the wetland.
- Follow existing trails or possible pathways where animals might be occurring; practically, clumped vegetation does not seem like a place used by mammals.
- Due to the nature of the wetland, a designed trail or path may be disrupted; therefore, bypassing an obstacle to regain the path later might be a sound option.

Night surveys

- Main materials are: head torches, digital cameras, binoculars; the most common night mammals (apart from bats, not concerned by this work, and primates not occurring in the wetland used as a case study) are mostly night carnivores.
- The researcher will prioritize areas that have been visited before (reconnaissance) or are known for their potential and knowledge about night mammals.
- The researcher will walk slowly with precautions in the dark, with the silence as necessary, to avoid disturbing animals and risking physical accidents.
- Be aware of possible animal attacks and be mindful of the measures in case of risks.
- Lighting infrequently and steadily at variable distances, especially when hearing or sensing the presence of animals.

7. Datasheet for the survey of small mammals from live traps (Sherman and pitfall traps)

Survey team: **Habitat**
 **Start time**
Day & date:

Site name:

Time	Trapline No	First capture (Yes/ No)	Species/ Genus/ Family	Age class	Sex	Morphometrics					Fur color and other external features	Special note	Photos
						Mass	BL	HFL	TL	EL			

Note: For measurements: BL = body length, HFL = hind foot length, EL = ear length, TL = tail length
 For age class Ad. = adult, S. Ad. = sub-adult, Juv. = juvenile, Young; for Sex F = Female, M = Male

